

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE FIRST TURKOLOGICAL CONGRESS AND THE PRINCIPLE OF ECONOMY IN THE LANGUAGE SYSTEM

Hasanova K.

PhD in Philology, Associate Professor

Dean of the Faculty of Philology, Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University

<https://orcid.org/0001-0001-8795-252X>

ABSTRACT

Regardless of their agglutinative or inflectional nature, all languages of the world possess the capacity to manifest the principle of linguistic economy in one form or another. At the First Turkological Congress convened in Baku on February 26, 1926, a wide range of issues—such as the alphabet, spelling and orthography, terminology, methods of language teaching, the interaction of related and neighboring languages, the literary language of Turkic languages, the theory of a proto-language, and the history of Turkic languages—were discussed and interpreted. Within the framework of these discussions, attention was also paid to the system of linguistic economy, and several of its characteristic features were briefly analyzed. This article aims to present an analytical perspective on that issue and to highlight how the principle of economy was implicitly addressed within the linguistic debates of the Congress.

Keywords: principle of economy; levels of the manifestation of economy; physiopsychological economy; reflection of this problem in Shcherba's report.

At the First Turkological Congress, Lev Vladimirovich Shcherba, who individually represented Russia, addressed the issue of economy in his report entitled “The Basic Principles of Orthography and Their Social Significance.” While discussing the four fundamental principles of orthography—phonetic, etymological, historical, and ideographic—he expressed certain views related to the economy of time, which undoubtedly referred to the ease and efficiency of reading a given material (11, p. 53).

In addressing linguistic economy, Professor Shcherba was the first in world linguistics to articulate a logical and convincing idea about achieving the expression of substantial meanings with minimal expenditure of energy. Naturally, the author's views—originally explained on the basis of the norms and rules of Russian orthography and orthoepy—are also fully applicable when extended to the phonetic laws of more than twenty-five Turkic languages. From this perspective, his views on orthography and orthoepy—particularly those concerning economy in the reading process—were unanimously welcomed with applause by the participants of the Congress. One of those who expressed clear support was Professor Lev Ivanovich Zhirkov of the Russian Association of Eastern Peoples. This Moscow-based scholar participated in the meeting as a co-rapporteur on orthographic issues and devoted considerable attention in his presentation to Shcherba's arguments. By substantiating Shcherba's ideas, he further elaborated on the issue of economy of time and articulated the following points in this regard. “I would like to substantiate what Professor Shcherba said about the importance of orthography as a social institution. He quite rightly points out that when we read a newspaper, we immediately perceive words with our eyes, which results in saving time, and this economy occurs on a nationwide scale for everyone. If you pick up a newspaper and there is a mistake in it, you begin to waste time, because you start thinking: why is it written

this way, perhaps it is a printing error, perhaps it indicates something, perhaps it is simply a mistake—and in doing so you lose time. If, as enterprises concerned with the scientific organization of labor do, one were to calculate all the time losses caused by the imperfection of orthography, the result would be an enormous amount of time lost by a nation due to deficiencies in orthography and the fact that many people do not know it properly. I encounter this issue very often; it is a particularly sensitive matter for me. In Moscow, I have students who study Persian, and when they translate from Persian into Russian, I require them to write using correct Russian orthography.”

“They object, they do not want to do it, but I tell them that refusing to write the way everyone else writes means committing a crime and stealing the nation's time. Therefore, for the Turks—whose orthography has been developed less than that of many other peoples—I consider orthographic issues to be among the central matters of this Congress. In my opinion, your decision will have a serious impact on the future fate of Turkic orthography” (2, 157–158). From the quotation we have presented extensively from his speech, it becomes clear that he attached greater importance to the linguo-social dimension of linguistic economy, or to the strong semantic relationship between language and culture. In this sense, the linguocultural aspects of the principle of economy found their first embryonic reflection here in world linguistics. Both Shcherba and Zhirkov, in their reports, focused primarily on the orthographic and orthoepic aspects of the principle of economy, substantiating their views by providing rich examples related to the differences between pronunciation and spelling.

It is well known that, historically, terminological lexical units related to various fields of science, economy, and agriculture entered the Turkic languages rapidly from Arabic and Persian, as well as from European languages. While the incorporation of religious and other related terms into Turkic languages dates back to

the 8th century, the influx of European lexical items corresponds mainly to the mid-19th and early 20th centuries. Borrowings from Russian, however, became much more extensive beginning in the first decades of the 20th century.

Extensive information on this issue is presented in the report entitled “On the Principles of the Formation of Scientific Terminology in the Turkic Languages” by the Estonian literary scholar Simunyagi Artur Rudolfovich Ziffeld. In his presentation, the speaker emphasized that even after making use of all dialects and vernaculars of the folk language, certain gaps would still remain in the literary languages with regard to terminology. To fill these gaps, he outlined the necessity of adhering to several principles, presented in four key points, one of which directly concerned the psychophysiological aspect of linguistic economy. These factors were reflected in his speech as follows:

1. The borrowed word must not exceed the phonetic limits characteristic of the recipient language (for example, it should not contain the “ü” affricate); 2) the borrowed word may only include sound correspondences and phonetic features inherent to the recipient language (for example, the word should not begin with a consonant diphthong); 3) the borrowed word must comply with the language’s harmony rules; 4) in terms of the speaker’s psychophysical economy, it is essential to strictly maintain the general stylistic norm of the language (3, p.177). As seen from the fourth point, the speaker emphasized that the psychophysiological aspect of linguistic economy is closely linked with the stylistic characteristics of any given language. In the world, due to the development and complexity of science, economics, technology, agriculture, political life, and similar fields, a significant number of specialized and abbreviated terms have emerged in various languages. In his report, Ziffeld touches upon these terms and evaluates them as units of time-saving, stating that:

“Our Azerbaijani intellectuals are debating: should abbreviated words such as ‘komandarm,’ ‘ispolkom,’ ‘NEP,’ ‘VES,’ etc., be incorporated? We are fully convinced that not only can they be, but they must, because abbreviated words convey maximum meaning in minimal time. Abbreviated words began to emerge in Germany even before the war, during the period of intense capitalist development. As you may recall, in Russia, abbreviated words started appearing during the world war period. In military technology, conciseness and time-saving are essential. ‘Glavkoverkh,’ ‘komandarm’—these are not Soviet words; they predate the Soviet era. The Soviet regime generated mostly new words. The Turkic languages will inevitably follow this example” (3, 178). After the October Revolution, the incorporation of abbreviated words—lexical units formed by retaining only the initial letters or first syllables and omitting the remaining parts—into Turkic languages, including Azerbaijani Turkish, accelerated even further. In the field of terminology, A. Zeynally, in his joint report “On the Scientific Terminology System for Turkic Languages,” briefly described such abbreviations as a form of formal economy (4, 187). Therefore, the content discussed at the Congress regarding linguistic economy largely corresponds to

these practices. However, some participants from Turkic nations also expressed additional opinions on linguistic economy, which were not recorded in the stenographic materials. For example, the contributions of Azerbaijani Turkish representative Abdulla Tagiyev, a student at the Leningrad Institute of Oriental Languages and Literature, and the Uzbek representative, teacher Khalid Said Khojajev, who was individually invited from Baku, were not recorded in the stenographic materials. However, these authors further developed, generalized, and refined their presentations in the years following the Congress, culminating in the joint publication of their book *Müxtəsər Üslubiyat* in Baku in 1933. In this work, they provided a detailed explanation of the aspects of linguistic economy, including elements such as questions, points, permissions, abbreviations, and substitutions. In the work, the following explanation is given regarding the question indicator: “Sometimes the subject, sometimes the predicate, and sometimes one or several secondary elements of the sentence are omitted, and occasionally all sentence elements are omitted, with the idea expressed by these omitted elements conveyed through a single separate word. For example, when someone asks ‘Has the teacher arrived?’ we respond with ‘Arrived.’ Here, the word ‘Arrived’ represents a sentence in which the subject has been omitted” (5, p. 39).

In the point factor, purpose and intonation are taken as the basis. For instance, the title of the collection may be Revolution and Culture or expressed as It is Revolution and Culture. High-intonation abbreviations are also included, such as Fire! Airplane! Telephone! (meaning “There is a fire,” “The airplane is flying,” “The telephone is ringing”) (5, p. 41).

The permission factor refers to shared words included in various symptomatic parts: In the permission factor, an example is: “You gave the money, and I spent it” (5, p. 41).

In the ellipsis factor, the omission of parallel elements in consecutive sentences is considered. For instance: “I have read all of Lenin’s works. You have read all of Lenin’s works” becomes simply “I have read all of Lenin’s works. You have read” (5, p. 41), and so on.

In the substitution factor, the focus is on the substantivization of adjectives, i.e., their ability to replace nouns. For example: “Those who worked passed the exam well, while those who didn’t were expelled from school.” Here, although those who worked and those who didn’t serve as subjects, logically the main subjects are the nouns they define. These sentences can be completed as: “The students who worked passed the exam well, while the students who didn’t were expelled from school” (5, p. 41).

Over the 100 years since the Congress, there was a stagnation in research on linguistic economy in the Turkological field between 1940 and 1960. Starting from the 1960s, separate publications and monographs on this topic began to appear among Russian, European, and Turkic scholars. In both foreign and local literature, approaches to the principle of linguistic economy have been multi-faceted, and to this day, stylistic, grammatical, and psycholinguistic types of economy each encompass specific subtypes of economization. In

our view, it would be more accurate to include phonological-morphological, lexical-semantic, and syntactic indicators under the stylistic type of economy, while the psycholinguistic types should encompass linguo-cognitive, explicit, and implicit speech elements. For example, one of our Azerbaijani scholars who approached the principle of economy from a stylistic perspective, Ə. Dəmirçizadə, in his fundamental work *Azərbaycanca Dilin Üslubiyatı* published in 1962, preferred using terms such as “abbreviation,” “shortening,” and “laconicization” more actively instead of the phrase “principle of economy,” which, in essence, condition the concept of economy itself. Ə. Dəmirçizadə considers certain violations of the general language norm to be acceptable, characterizing them as forms of linguistic concessions. The researcher discusses the variety of such concessions and notes that some, as a result, create entirely new categories. For instance, in possessive constructions, the omission of the possessive case has ultimately led to the formation of a specific grammatical rule—expressions such as *şəhərin qapısı* (“city’s gate”) or *dağın başı* (“mountain top”) evolved alongside forms like *şəhər qapısı* and *dağ başı*, which became standardized. Therefore, we consider such cases not as exceptions to a rule but as established norms within modern Azerbaijani. The analysis throughout the work demonstrates that the researcher emphasizes the phonological-morphological type of stylistic economy, offering scientifically and logically valuable propositions.

The term “linguistic economy” was first used in Azerbaijani philology by Z. Budaqova. In 1970, in her collection of articles Stylistics of the Azerbaijani Literary Language, published by Elm Publishing House, she thoroughly examined the section on “types of sentences according to purpose and intonation.” In the subsection on imperative sentences, she extensively employed the expression “used economically” to demonstrate that “elliptical imperative sentences are widely used in literary works.” The omission of certain words in these sentences further enhances the expressiveness of the idea, making it figurative and economical while emphasizing the main purpose. Some of these sentences carry the character of a request or command (7, p. 281). The thematic content of the author’s study indicates that she favored the linguo-syntactic type of economy, generalizing her observations according to this type of economy.

Among the components of syntactic repetitions, the fonomorphological and linguo-syntactic types of the economy principle are most prominently manifested. Extensive scientific and theoretical insights on this topic can be found in M. Adilov’s monograph *Syntactic Repetitions in the Azerbaijani Language*. Similar to Ə. Dəmirçizadə, Adilov preferred to use terms such as “shortening,” “specialization,” and “condensation” instead of the explicit expression “economy” (8; 18, pp. 26–32).

In Azerbaijani linguistics, there are research studies on the principle of economy in which the fonomorphological, formal, structural, and psycholinguistic types of linguistic economy are integrated, and the re-

search directions are carried out from these perspectives. For example, the most comprehensive study on linguistic economy in Azerbaijani was first conducted by H. Yusifov. In 1976, he defended his candidate dissertation on the topic *Economy in the Language System (Based on Azerbaijani Language Materials)*, in which he analyzed crucial aspects of economy through a rigorous evaluative framework. According to the scholar, it “is a regular linguistic phenomenon in the language and determines the emergence of certain norms” (9, p. 4). The researcher considered the communicative function of language as the main criterion for economy in the language system, evaluating elements that deviate from this function as economical forms, and extensively discussed the importance of using this criterion in determining various language norms (9, p. 4). In this study, which is divided into three chapters, the scholar analyzed the principle of economy at the levels of phonemes, morphemes, and sentences, and supported his theoretical claims with abundant examples drawn from literary works and spoken language.

In 2008, the Linguistics Encyclopedia published by Mütərcim Publishing highlighted the psycho-physiological type of the economy principle, stating that “the law of economy [expenditure of minimal effort], characterized as one of the factors influencing language changes, essentially enables the speaker to express their thought with minimal energy. The law of economy manifests at all levels [layers] of language. Based on the principle of expending minimal effort, the law of economy results in the reduction or omission of sounds, sound combinations, and syllables in various positions of words in Azerbaijani, for example: [sora → sonra, savayı → savay], [Tarverdi → Tanrıverdi], [tabelik → tabelilik], etc. “At the level of word formation, various abbreviations, contractions, and compound words formed from word combinations are also considered units and phenomena related to the principle of economy” (10, p. 425). From the general content and meaning of this brief overview, it is evident that the statements made here fully correspond to, and align with, what Shcherba and Ziffeldin discussed regarding psychophysiological economy at the Turkological Congress.

“Examples in poetry demonstrate economy at the phonemic, morphemic, lexemic, semiotic, and syntactic levels, and in each line, stanza, and complete text, one encounters language rich in economy. On this subject, M. Huseynov, in his monograph *Dil və Poeziya (Language and Poetry)*, provides brief commentary, noting—based on the stylistic type of economy—that ‘the conciseness of meaning volume is such an indivisible unity in which all shades of a word and its semantic-stylistic potential are utilized to the maximum in poetic activity’” (11, p. 70).

“The researcher K. Həbibova, in her article *A Psycholinguistic Interpretation of the Economy Principle in the Language of the ‘Kitabi Dədə-Qorqud’ Epics* published in *Türkologiya*, 2011, Issue IV, traced the economy principle through ellipsis, linking it to the psychological states of the characters in the epics. Based on numerous examples, she demonstrates that

her approach leans toward a linguo-cognitive understanding of economy. According to the researcher, ‘Due to the economy principle manifesting in human psychology, only those linguistic phenomena remain stable and effective in which minimal respiratory effort, ease of memorization, and invariability of form are combined. From this perspective, syntactic constructions with elliptical forms enjoy semantic freedom in grammatical completion’” (12, pp. 75–76).

“Ə. Abdullayev, Y. Seyidov, and A. Həsənov, in their 2002 publication *Müasir Azərbaycan dili* (Modern Azerbaijani Language), particularly in the section on simple sentences in the syntax chapter intended for higher education students, approached the economy principle from a linguistic-structural perspective, providing abundant examples illustrating the manifestation levels of such syntactic units” (13, pp. 205–215).

“K. Abdulla, in his 2016 textbook *Azərbaycan dili sintaksisinin nəzəri problemləri* (Theoretical Problems of Azerbaijani Syntax), specifically in the section *The Function of Sentence Members in Azerbaijani*, examined the principle of linguistic economy from a theoretical-linguistic perspective. He analyzed cases of laconic expression, compactness, and abbreviation as they manifest in the syntactic nature of sentence elements within a text, explaining that these phenomena arise from the specific communicative roles and functions of sentence members and the functional value of language means within the complete syntactic structure. He concluded that ‘the manifestation of the economy principle within a sentence primarily occurs due to the ellipsis of one or another sentence member’ (14, pp. 91–92; 72).”

“K. Abdullayev, linking ellipsis comprehensively with the suppressive phenomenon, notes that ‘its [suppressive-K.H.] salient feature is that, within a sentence, it can be easily restored at any time depending on the speaker’s intention or desire’ (14, p. 92). He precisely establishes the parallelism between ellipsis and mental representation, emphasizing that ‘ellipsis, i.e., the omission of a sentence member, does not mean that it has not occupied its proper syntactic position; it is not “forgotten.” Its presence can be realized through the sentence’s position, which is conditioned by the broader text and situational context. In this way, ellipsis is “recalled” or filled’ (14, p. 93). K. Abdullayev proposes three directions for the restoration of ellipsis in the Azerbaijani language and examines each of these directions separately in his work (15, pp. 93–98).”

The author, in their 2022 study titled “Levels of Manifestation of the Linguistic Economy Principle in Azerbaijani Prose Texts”, in the subchapter “Analysis of Economy from a Psycholinguistic Perspective”, approaches the principle of linguistic economy from pragmatic, sociological, linguocultural, mass communication, and communicative perspectives. The study demonstrates that “the principle of economy is, in general, a significant problem in linguistics. This principle is conditioned by various extralinguistic factors. It is influenced by psychological, psychophysiological, and social factors (such as the memory and cognition of language users, and the situational contexts of their interactions). The theory of economy actualizes general

ideas in language and speech, defines the anthropocentric orientation of language, and contributes to the development of pragmalinguistics, mass communication theory, stylistics, and speech culture” (16, pp. 18–19).

Thus, the study of the principle of linguistic economy in the Azerbaijani language and its literary-stylistic system is presented in approximately this manner. By comparison, foreign scholarly literature provides more extensive investigations of this linguistic phenomenon. In the global linguistic landscape, the tendency toward economy in languages with different systems was first studied by Boduende Kurtene. In addition to identifying several factors essential for the emergence of this tendency, he emphasized the significant role of development from concreteness to abstraction (17, p. 56). This indicates that the author approached the principle of economy from the perspective of the strong mutual semantic connection between language and culture, thereby encompassing a linguocultural dimension.

In Russian linguistics, A. Martini was the first to extensively apply the principle of economy at the phoneme level. In his 1960 work, *The Principle of Economy and Phonetic Phenomena*, he analyzed economy in the language system through phenomena such as sound loss, assimilation, dissimilation, and metathesis using a historical-comparative method. This approach revealed the characteristic factors underlying these processes (18, p. 101), which, in our view, can appropriately be regarded as a linguo-phonetic perspective.

The Russian linguist Y. M. Lotman published his monograph *Analysis of the Poetic Text* in 1970, in which he expressed and highlighted the principle of linguistic economy in poetic language as a prominent scholarly position and leitmotif. He noted that a relatively short poem can convey information that a multi-volume non-literary text cannot express (19, p. 35). In another work, Lotman explored in detail the specific spectra of the economy principle in poetic language (20, pp. 45–81). The basis of Lotman’s reflections on the principle of economy clearly lies in the linguo-structural type of approach, which is characterized by the fact that the principle of economy serves as a crucial linguistic attribute for the text and its structural organization.

The Russian linguist V. A. Serebrennikov examined the principle of linguistic economy from a linguocultural perspective, giving particular attention to its psychophysiological aspects. He wrote: “At the root of the tendency toward economy lies the human organism. In language, the principle of economy manifests as a specific form of self-preservation instinct. It is a unique reaction against the overexertion of physiological tension, countering any form of discomfort that complicates memory functioning and interferes with certain brain functions involved in speech production and perception” (21, p. 22).

The Russian researcher I. F. Vardul investigated the principle of economy at the language level from a stylistic perspective, associating it primarily with suppressiveness. According to the researcher, “to ellipsis the syntactic-semantic unit (‘sintaksemi’) is to econo-

mize its content” (22, p. 63). Although the author expresses this idea concisely, it conveys to the reader that he attributed significant importance to the linguo-structural and semantic type of economy.

In English linguistics, Jespersen briefly related the different types and forms of economy to the ellipsization of certain sentence elements, noting that “expression is what the speaker gives, whereas economy is what he could give but does not” (23, p. 359).

The French linguist S. Balli examined linguistic economy from conceptual and situational perspectives and explicitly summarized these in his work *General Linguistics and Issues of the French Language*. Conceptual and situational economy, according to Balli, means that in his studies, he approached this linguistic phenomenon from a linguo-magnetic perspective, noting that “ellipses in words, word combinations, and sentence models economized in a text can be restored with the help of context and the syntactic whole” (24, p. 99).

Each method reflects the natural development of the language and responds to various purposes linked to its cultural and social life (Ismayil, 2024). Q. Paul emphasized that forms of linguistic economy, even when not actively used, are represented in the language-consciousness, that is, in thought within the brain, carrying both concrete and abstract meanings. He noted that “in this context, abstraction should be considered one of the primary factors for achieving an economized state” (25, p. 95).

The Russian orientalist and distinguished linguist V. V. Vinogradov, discussing the factors that determine economy in poetic contexts, emphasized the structural type of this principle, noting that “the work of a poet can only be compared to the skillful labor of a master jeweler. After all, a word is like gold” (26, p. 22).

Conclusion

From the analysis of these studies, it can be summarized that at the First Turkological Congress, Shcherba and Ziffeld briefly addressed the principle of linguistic economy primarily from a physiopsychological perspective. This marked the first embryonic conceptualization of one of the essential aspects of this linguistic phenomenon in the global linguistic context. Over the subsequent century, the principle of economy has been theoretically investigated across its various types and categories. However, despite this theoretical elaboration, the exploration of the concept of economy in poetry—particularly its unique linguo-cultural and semiotic characteristics—remains underdeveloped. The studies conducted so far have primarily focused on structural, phonological, syntactic, and pragmatic aspects, while the cultural, cognitive, and stylistic dimensions of poetic economy have not been systematically addressed. Therefore, this gap highlights the necessity of a dedicated research endeavor that examines how linguistic economy operates within literary texts, how it interacts with cultural and cognitive factors, and how it contributes to the efficiency, expressivity, and aesthetic density of poetic discourse. Such a study would not only deepen our understanding of the principle of economy in the Azerbaijani language and other Turkic languages but would also provide valuable insights into

the intersection of language, cognition, and culture in literary expression.

References

1. Shcherba, L.V. (2006). The main principles of orthography and their social significance. I Baku Turkological Congress, February 26, 1926. Translated from Russian, foreword and commentary by K.V. Narimanoglu & A. Agakishiev. Baku: Chinar, pp. 152–156.
2. Hirkov, L.I. (2006). Co-report on “The main principles of orthography and their social significance”. I Baku Turkological Congress, February 26, 1926. Translated from Russian, foreword and commentary by K.V. Narimanoglu & A. Agakishiev. Baku: Chinar, pp. 156–158.
3. Ziffeld, S.A.R. (2006). On the principles of scientific terminology in Turkic languages. I Baku Turkological Congress materials. Baku: Chinar, pp. 172–178.
4. Zeynalı, A. (2006). On the scientific terminology system in Turkic languages. I Baku Turkological Congress materials. Baku: Chinar, pp. 183–187.
5. Tağızadə, A., & Xocayev, X.C. (1933). *Müxtəsər üslubiyat*. Baku.
6. Dəmirçizadə, Ə.M. (1962). The stylistics of the Azerbaijani language. Baku, 271 pp.
7. Budaqova, Z.İ. (1970). Types of sentences according to purpose of expression, In *Stylistics of Azerbaijani literary language*. Baku: Elm, pp. 263–280.
8. Adilov, M.İ. (1974). Syntactic repetitions in the Azerbaijani language. Baku: Elm, pp. 23–31.
9. Yusifov, M.İ. (1976). Economy in the language system (based on Azerbaijani materials). Candidate of Philology dissertation. Baku, 169 pp.
10. *Encyclopedia of Linguistics* (2008). Vol. II. Baku: Münəccim, 528 pp.
11. Hüseynov, M. (2008). *Language and poetry*. Baku: Elm, 434 pp.
12. Həbibova, K. (2011). Psycholinguistic interpretation of the principle of economy in the language of the “Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud” epics. *Türkologiya*, 4, 75–83.
13. Abdullayev, Ə., Seyidov, Y., & Həsənov, A. (2002). *Modern Azerbaijani language: Syntax*. Baku: Şərq-Qərb, pp. 445.
14. Abdullayev, K.M. (2016). *Theoretical problems of Azerbaijani syntax*. 2nd revised edition. Baku: MTM-Innovation, 360 pp.
15. Abdullayev, K.M. (1999). *Theoretical problems of Azerbaijani syntax*. Baku, 282 pp.
16. Həsənova, K.N. (2022). Manifestations of the principle of linguistic economy in Azerbaijani prose texts. PhD dissertation. Baku, 151 pp.
17. Bodig de Kirtane, I.A. (1969). Some general observations on language. In *Selected Works on General Linguistics*. Moscow: AN USSR, Vol. I.
18. Martine, A. (1960). Principles of economy in phonetic changes. Moscow, 263 pp.
19. Lotman, Y.N. (1970). *Structure of a literary text*. Moscow, 384 pp.
20. Lotman, Y.N. (1972). *Analysis of poetic text: Structure of verse*. Leningrad, 221 pp.

21. Serebrennikov, B.A. (1974). Probabilistic foundations in comparative studies. Moscow.
22. Vardul, I.F. (1960). On the phenomenon of ellipsis. Moscow, pp. 63–72.
23. Jespersen, O. (1958). Philosophy of Grammar. Moscow, 329 pp.
24. Balli, S. (1955). General linguistics and issues of the French language. Moscow, 412 pp.
25. Radlov, V.V. (1983). Experience of Turkic dictionaries. S.G.B., 1160 pp.
26. Vinogradov, V.V. (1971). On the theory of poetic reception. Moscow: Higher School, 240 pp.
27. Ismayil, Z. (2024, April). Development points of the derivation process related to Nakhchivan dialects and accents (based on written and oral literary and artistic examples). In Forum for Linguistic Studies (Transferred), 6(2), 1192.